

Wild Smoke: Managing Forest Pollution in Northern British Columbia since 1950

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ABSTRACT

Almost every year, ash drifts from forest fires in north-western Canada into northern Europe, altering forecasts on both continents, settling in Antarctic ice and turning the skies over the world's major cities an apocalyptic orange. As smoke drifts from the forests into nearby communities and distant urban centres, it becomes the medium through which most people experience forest fire, leaving traces on memories and bodies. Although wildfires and their associated plumes are getting worse, people have a long and dynamic relationship with forest fire smoke which can be understood through the lens of air pollution and forestry history. Using British Columbia, Canada as a case study, I argue that the difficulty of separating wildfire smoke from other types of air pollution has worked to the advantage of land managers interested in supporting the forestry industry, with negative impacts for northern communities.

KEYWORDS

Air pollution, forestry, wildfire, northern history, land management

'Forest Fires Cast Pall On Northeast; Canadian Drift 600 Miles Long Darkens Wide Areas and Arouses "Atom" Fears'¹

'Scots See Blue Sun, Fear End of World',²

'Solen og månen ble koboltblå!' ('The sun and the moon became cobalt blue!')³

1. *New York Times*, 25 Sept. 1950, 1.

2. *Northern Whig*, 27 Sept. 1950, 4.

3. *Verdens Gang*, 28 Sept. 1950, 8.

These headlines graced newspapers from New York to Edinburgh to Oslo in the fall of 1950. The 3.5-million-acre Chinchaga fire in the Peace River district of northern British Columbia (BC) and Alberta had sent particulate high into the atmosphere. As it drifted east, smoke from the Chinchaga fire obscured the sun, changed the colour of light and even cooled the ambient air temperature. By October, it had completely circumnavigated the earth and come back to deposit black carbon in Alaskan ice.⁴

In the twenty-first century, more smoke than ever is flowing out of the forest and into communities near and far. Since July 2015 the European Union's Copernicus Atmospheric Monitoring system has recorded regular instances of forest fire smoke plumes crossing the Atlantic from North America as a result of intensifying wildfire seasons. Although all forest fires produce smoke, it takes a burn of significant size and violence to loft plumes above the planetary boundary layer into the free troposphere where they can be transported long distances. Especially large, hot and aggressive wildfires create cumulous plumes that can go even higher, punching through the tropopause and into the stratosphere.⁵ Such fires are among the world's largest, and most of them occur in the boreal forests ringing the northern hemisphere between about 50°N and 70°N.

As smoke drifts from the forests into nearby communities and distant urban centres, it becomes the medium through which most people experience forest fire. Rather than as evacuees or firefighters, most of us are recipients of the particulate drifting into densely populated spaces. Although encounters with smoke might feel less dramatic than confrontations with a flame front, the impacts of breathing it in should not be underestimated. New research on the impacts of transient smoke suggest that it kills more than 339,000 people globally per year and contains more harmful toxins than other types of air pollution.⁶ But the impact is more than physical. The scale and intensity of major fire and smoke events creates a sense of 'wrongness' in the environment as people breathe particulate-laden air on a seasonal basis and rhetorically link their experiences to the unprecedented conditions created by climate change.⁷

4. Cordy Tymstra, *The Chinchaga Firestorm: When the Moon and Sun Turned Blue* (Edmonton: University of Alberta Press, 2015), p. 86.

5. Michael Fromm and Rene Servranckx, 'Transport of forest fire smoke above the tropopause by supercell convection', *Geophysical Research Letters* **30** (10) (2003): 49.

6. Two thirds of deaths due to smoke occur in sub-Saharan Africa and Southeast Asia, suggesting inequality in terms of who bears the greatest burdens of climate change. Fay Johnston et. al., 'Estimated global mortality attributable to smoke from landscape fires', *Environmental Health Perspectives* **120** (5) (2012): 695–701. New research on wildfire smoke toxicity from Rosana Aguilera et. al., 'Wildfire smoke impacts respiratory health more than fine particles from other sources: observational evidence from Southern California', *Nature Communications* **12** (1493) (2021): <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-21708-0>

7. Alastair Gee, 'Is this the end of forests as we've known them?' *The Guardian*, 10 March 2021 (accessed 2 June 2021): <https://t.co/IAHJa0faBx?amp=1>

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Our twenty-first century relationships with smoke are the products of culture and history. Forest fire smoke's natural mobility has long made it a source of tension and negotiation between people, their governments and the forestry industry. Although big fires could send smoke almost anywhere, communities along the edge of the boreal forest have most often been on the front lines of these tensions and negotiations. As it drifted across time and space, smoke carried the burdens of culturally-ascribed meaning even as it loaded human bodies with ash and anxiety.

Smoke research is complicated by the medium's unpredictability and the fact that, once airborne, it becomes difficult to keep track of in the archives or elsewhere. People did not always notice smoke and, when they did, they often did not understand what they were looking at. This characteristic ephemerality is critical for understanding how smoke has been received by people over time. Because it is difficult to pin down, smoke is a convenient receptacle for human ideas about the environment. Appearing out of the sky mysteriously and according to its own schedules, smoke could be anything. As the headlines at the top of this article suggest, smoke could signal an outbreak of hostilities between states, the end of the world or an interesting scientific phenomenon. There also were speculations that the smoke was actually dust from Egypt or pollution from German factories.⁸ The way people responded to smoke said more about their own anxieties and worldviews than about the nature of the smoke itself. Smoke is not alone among the forces of nature in its utility as a receptacle for human meaning-making, but its ephemerality combined with the distances it travelled made it particularly susceptible to contradiction across time and space. As it drifted over the land and water, it meant different things for different people. Specifically, as smoke drifted out of boreal forests and into populated spaces, it became an avenue for distant environmental ideals to flow in the opposite direction. Like ash settling in arctic ice, the impacts are uneven and difficult to trace. Yet, by following the path they carved in the atmosphere, we can begin to understand how dominant environmental ideals functionally impacted massive landscapes in the late twentieth century.

In this article I follow the history of the BC Forest Service in western Canada to show how human-smoke relations changed as a result of forest smoke's entanglement with clean air initiatives in one of the world's smokiest jurisdictions. I argue that the forestry industry, regulated and managed by the BC Forest Service, had a stake in the perception of forest smoke as 'natural' in order to normalise its own wood smoke pollution, especially in the province's single-resource communities. The rise of environmentalism in the late twentieth century, and especially the growth of attention to air pollution, changed perceptions of smoke by the late 1970s in the northern hemisphere's urban spaces. Although forest smoke could usually be distinguished from industrial smoke, both proved a nuisance and, in some cases, an existential threat. By

8. 'Blue Sun', *Evening Telegraph and Post*, 26 Sept. 1950, 1.

the 1980s, institutions charged with wildfire management ended up in the difficult position of navigating rising anti-pollution sentiment along with the very real need to continue allowing smoke into the atmosphere for the health of both ecology and industry in forested lands.⁹ Unable to adequately distinguish between ‘wild’ and industrial pollution, forest managers became unwitting arbitrators between smoke and its detractors. The Forest Service failed to anticipate the extent to which the rhetorical power of urban air pollution could influence land management operations far beyond city limits.

Smoke highlights the connectivity between people and land because it physically connects people to distant environments they may only otherwise understand in abstraction. Following the Chinchaga fire in 1950, the Norwegians, English, Scots, Danes, Americans and Canadians who breathed in smoke from the fire at the headwaters of the Peace River involuntarily incorporated pieces of burned forest into their bodies, linking them materially to BC and its land management practices. The path carved through the upper atmosphere by Chinchaga smoke transgressed the imagined boundaries between people and what they perceived as distant wilderness. The cultural and intellectual tools they used to make sense of those connections are particularly important to understand in the twenty-first century when more humans than ever are being exposed to forest smoke. By following historic smoke out of the forest and into our communities over the last century, we gain valuable contextual data for modern climate pathologies and anxieties.¹⁰ Wherever smoke went, it left traces that settled unevenly on memories and bodies.

WHAT IS WILDFIRE SMOKE?

Smoke results from incomplete combustion, when a fire cannot get sufficient oxygen to burn cleanly and so releases waste into the air. The dark clouds we see rising from burning material are collections of microscopic, unburned particles carried away from the flames by rising heat. In the forest, these particles

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9. Over the study period, the body in charge of BC’s forests was known as the Department of Lands, Forest Branch (1912–1945); The Department of Lands and Forests, Forest Service (1945–1962); and the Department of Lands, Forests, and Water Resources, Forest Service (1962–1975). The Wildfire Branch was created in 1912. ‘British Columbia Forest Service History’, Ministry Library, Ministry of Forests, Lands, and Natural Resource Operations, last updated April 2013 (accessed 14 June 2021), <https://www.for.gov.bc.ca/hfd/library/history.htm>
 10. In Australia, Phil Manus proposes ‘that understanding smoke as part of atmospheres within which humans live and breathe is necessary to support the integrated management of land, water, air and the living entities in and beyond a particular area or country. A more-than-urban political ecology of smoke will assist people to view themselves and their welfare as being connected with what happens on spaces that are physically distant.’ Phil McManus, ‘A more-than-urban political ecology of bushfire smoke in eastern Australia, 2019–2020’, *Australian Geographer* (April 2021): <https://doi.org/10.1080/00049182.2021.1946244>

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most often include tiny pieces of tar, ash, oils and carbon. When a plane from Leuchars, Scotland returned from an investigative flight following the Chinchaga blue moon in September 1950, its wings were reportedly covered in a fine film of oil.¹¹ As smoke moves away from the fire and interacts with the atmosphere, it changes. It may disperse, change elevation or interact with other components. For example, interaction with sunlight changes the nitrous acid in forest smoke into hydroxyl radical and nitric oxide, the key ingredients that drive the formation of ozone.¹²

All kinds of smoke are harmful to human health because they contain fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) which can travel deep into the lungs and cause inflammation and irritation. Recent research suggests that wildfire smoke can be more harmful than other sources of ambient PM_{2.5} partly because it contains unpredictable mixes of chemical compounds based on the kinds of material it burns through.¹³ From a chemical or biological perspective, forest fire smoke is indistinguishable from other types of biomass burning, such as clearing for agriculture or wood burning for heat in homes because its character depends on fuel type, which varies from fire to fire.¹⁴

Smoke is most accurately understood as occupying a sprawling spectrum of relative toxicity, and resists the neat categories required for effective regulation. Various administrative bodies have attempted to differentiate wildfire smoke from other kinds of smoke, based on character of its originating fires. Canada's Natural Resources ministry uses the term 'wildland fire' rather than 'wildfire' to refer to burns and their smoke, thus eliminating the need to determine whether a fire was intentionally or unintentionally ignited. This strategy recruits a geographical distinction that (mostly) filters out industrially or domestically generated smoke while encompassing fires that both are and are not controlled, but only in Canada's designated 'wildland' areas.¹⁵ The American Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) offers perhaps the clearest distinction between different types of fires and their smokes. It differentiates legally between *wildfires*, *wildland use fires* and *prescribed burning*. Under its regulations, wildfires are 'unplanned' and 'unwanted', wildland use fires are those that are unintentionally ignited but allowed to burn in accordance with

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11. 'Forest Fires caused Blue Sun and Moon', *The Fifeshire Advertiser*, 13 Nov. 1954,
 12. Lu Xu et al. 'Ozone chemistry in Western U.S. wildfire plumes', *Science Advances* 7 (50): <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.abl3648>
 13. R. Aguilera, T. Corringham, A. Gershunov et al., 'Wildfire smoke impacts respiratory health more than fine particles from other sources: observational evidence from Southern California', *Nature Communications* 12 (1493) (2021): <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-21708-0>
 14. Ongoing research in Greece has identified a connection between large-scale biomass burning from forest fires and brown carbon over large distances. The Pyrogenic Transformations Affective Climate and Health project is funded by the European Research Council, running from 1 June 2017 to 30 November 2023: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/726165>
 15. 'Forest Fires', Natural Resources Canada: <https://www.nrcan.gc.ca/our-natural-resources/forests/wildland-fires-insects-disturbances/forest-fires/13143> (accessed 8 June 2022).

land management plans, and prescribed fires are intentional burns lit by land managers for specific resource management objectives. In practice, however, these categories blend in unpredictable ways – for example, prescribed and use fires get out of control, and ‘unplanned’ wildfires provide necessary ecological functions whether or not they are in line with land management plans. Moreover, smoke drifts through the gaps of all these institutional categorisation strategies because it mixes with pollution from other sources as it moves, rendering its exact origins hard to trace.

History shows that the categorisation problem experienced by modern regulatory agencies is not new. Without prompting, international media called Chinchaga a wildfire, designating the plume an act of God beyond human control – a characterisation that may have fit with dominant ideas about the wild nature of Canada’s north in 1950. Closer to its ignition point, Chinchaga’s relative wildness becomes more ambiguous. BC and the Alberta Forest Services knew about, managed and used the fire over time. As Cody Tymstra writes in his history of the fire, a lookout spotted the first smoke on 2 June 1950 and reported it to the authorities. A ranger from the BC Forest Service drove out to investigate and found a fire burning through some old logging slash – a common source of explosive fuel in the north that would need to be burned by foresters anyway. Since the fire was not doing any harm (and was in fact taking care of some necessary clearing work) local rangers in both BC and Alberta kept an eye on it but took no action. A mix of unchecked and managed burning continued until September, when wind and weather worsened conditions unexpectedly and the fire grew aggressive. The Forest Service was open about the plume’s complex origins in its annual report for 1950:

New fires sprang up, old dormant fires revived, and settlers’ burning-fires got out of control, particularly between September 19th to 25th, when numerous acreages were burned. These fires burning in the outlying areas, mostly in scrub-timber types, plus similar fires in Alberta, caused a widespread smoke haze which received considerable publicity.¹⁶

Chinchaga, like most big fires and their smokes, stemmed from a variety of combustion sources and polluted the air under a shifting degree of human control.

In what follows, I refer to ‘forest fires’ and ‘forest smoke’ to describe burns curated to different extents by human beings in sparsely settled or ‘wilderness’ areas. Such distinctions remain imperfect. The slash burns instigated by forestry companies may have had more in common with the industrial stacks in urban centres than with lightning ignition in a remote pine stand. It was this very ambiguity that rendered urban concerns about air pollution disproportionately powerful in the woods.

16. Province of BC, *Report of the Forest Service, Year Ended December 31st 1950* (Victoria: King’s Printer, 1951), p. 48.

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THE HISTORY OF FOREST SMOKE IN BC

Ashes from heaven – raining down on Vancouver from an amber sky through which a blood-red sun shone weakly ... Like tiny flakes of snow the fine particles of ash from the worst forest fire in British Columbia's history drifted down to land gently on the shoulders of surprised Vancouver citizens ... like a huge orange in the sky, the sun cast a weird amber light over the city until it disappeared in the increasing western haze. There was no sunset.¹⁷

British Columbians, like many of their boreal neighbours, have a long relationship with forest fire smoke. The boreal halo that extends across northern Canada, Alaska, Scandinavia and Russia contains mixed fir, pine and spruce forests and is a fire-adapted ecosystem, meaning that local species depend on regular low-intensity burns to remain healthy. A rich archival and physical record tells the story of regular 'smoke seasons' within and around the boreal zone. Black carbon from major smoke events has regularly settled in ice and in the mud of lake beds in Northern Canada, Scandinavia, Greenland and Siberia for hundreds of thousands of years. Archival records offer the opportunity to corroborate core samples with human observations, starting with the advent of record keeping.¹⁸ Large-scale patterns are evident in the smoke record. In general, the twentieth century saw an increase in the scale and intensity of boreal forest fires in the global north, which fire scientists connect to a combination of suppression policy and climate change.

Among boreal communities, BC is a useful case study for understanding human relationships with smoke over time because it contains a mix of different fire ecologies across approximately a million square kilometres. Its large urban centres in both the provincial interior and along its southwest coast are regular recipients of smoke both from the northern boreal zone and from the active fire regimes in the American west, while fires in the boreal forests of the province's north regularly send smoke east across the North American continent and beyond. As a subject for historical study, the province is unique in the scale and consistency of its forest management regime. Partly because of its strong history of public ownership of its forested land (95 per cent of land is publicly owned) BC is considered an international leader in forestry and wildfire policy. The annual reports of its main forestry ministry (under various names) provide a complete record of its activities since the turn of the twentieth century.¹⁹ Consistency also stems from forestry's extraordinary power in BC. The province's economic prospects (and to a large extent its political,

17. 'City Enshrouded by Amber Pall of Forest Fire Smoke', *The Vancouver Sun*, 23 July 1938.

18. For example, the medieval warm period and the severe fire year of 1910 are both visible in the ice cores. Kaplan Talcin et. al., 'A 1000-yr record of forest fire activity from eclipse icefield, Yukon, Canada', *The Holocene* 16 (2)(2006): 200–09.

19. The body responsible for forestry in BC was known as the Forest Branch from 1912–1945 and the Forest Service from 1945–2010. It began under the Department of Lands, which

cultural and social ones, too) have long been tied to the industry. While not immune from the ebb and flow of politics and public opinion (as we shall see), BC's Forest Service enjoyed considerable latitude in choosing the direction of provincial forestry policy, even in the face of remarkable external pressures.²⁰

While smoke itself was not quantified, the BC Forest Branch traced the total amount of land burned from its inception in 1911. The amount of smoke produced can be roughly inferred. Importantly, the Forest Service divided these totals into 'intentional' and 'unintentional' burns until 1958 – a choice that reflects a tacit acknowledgement of the blurriness of forest fire categories and that both types of fires served land management functions. In 1922, 1925, 1931, 1958 and 1961 BC saw over 1,000,000 acres burned, with 1958 being the most severe fire year on record with more than 2,000,000 acres catching fire.²¹ The impact of suppression policy, and especially initial attack, becomes clear after this point. At the beginning of the century, a low fire year saw 41,000 acres burned (1913), while, by the end of the century and under an increasingly effective suppression regime, as few as 3,700 (1977) acres caught fire.²²

The impact of suppression on wildfire regimes is well understood, but what is more surprising is how *intentional* burning expanded in BC – and even exceeded the scale of natural ignitions by the 1960s.²³ For most of the 1930s, the Forest Service authorised many modest burns for a total of between twenty and thirty thousand fired acres (for logging, agriculture, roadways and other purposes). Starting in 1938, they authorised large scale burns that covered more land – from forty to fifty thousand acres total in the province annually. A build-up of slash from the depression became a Forest Service priority in 1941 and 1942, increasing the volume of burns still further. Through the 1950s the Forest Service consistently burned between sixty and eighty thousand acres annually, until the severe fire season of 1958 and a logging strike in 1959 put a temporary hold on their work. Throughout the 1960s, the Forest Service burned between sixty and ninety thousand acres. In 1967, the *Forest Act* extended provisions requiring slash burning from the Coast district to the entire province.²⁴ In the early years of the 1970s, which are the last years for which

evolved over the years into the Ministry of Forests (and was also responsible at different times for water, mines and range).

20. Jeremy Wilson, *Talk and Log: Wilderness Politics in British Columbia* (Vancouver: UBC Press, 1998), p. 29.
21. Province of BC, *Report of the Forest Service, Year Ended December 31st 1958* (Victoria: King's Printer, 1959), p. 15.
22. Province of BC, 'Forest fire damage', *Report of the Minister of Lands, Part II – Forest Branch, 1914* (Victoria: King's Printer: 1914), D88; 'Table 37 – Comparison of Loss Caused by Forest Fires in the Last 10 Years', Province of BC, *Report of the Forest Service, Year Ended December 31, 1977* (Victoria: King's Printer, 1978), Q52.
23. Wesley Brookes et al., 'A disrupted historical fire regime in Central British Columbia', *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution* 9 (2021): 1–14.
24. Province of BC, *Report of the Forest Service, Year Ended December 31, 1967* (Victoria: King's Printer, 1968), p. 13.

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the data is available in the annual reports, the Forest Service burned more than 100,000 acres every year.

The edges of the boreal forest have always been laced with smoke from diverse kinds of combustion, including a wide spectrum of natural and human ignitions. In its annual reports, the BC Forest Service carefully enumerated these sources. Lightning remained the most common cause, followed by careless recreationists, farmers, railways and construction. Yet the data on slash burning, carefully quantified by the Forest Service throughout these years, suggests that air pollution was exacerbated by the BC Forest Service at a steadily increasing rate after World War II. By moving freely across the entire spectrum of urban, suburban, rural and resource spaces, forest smoke connected spaces during the twentieth century, at a time when air pollution was becoming increasingly contentious.

SMOKE POLLUTION IN NORTHERN AND RESOURCE COMMUNITIES

Historians have traced how the exponential growth of cities, the concentration of industrial processes and the prevalent use of coal for energy culminated in pollution clouds that hung over cities around the world in the nineteenth and twentieth centuries. Industrial smoke stained clothing, blocked out the sun and damaged peoples' health.²⁵ Although smoky skies began as a sign of urban wealth, their unpleasant environmental and health effects provoked rising discontent, especially among those who bore the heaviest burdens of air pollution. Polluted urban spaces and a lack of fresh air became tied to the moral degradation of society under industrial capitalism. Smoke proved especially galvanising because it provided a common target for environmental reformers with divergent goals.²⁶ Anti-smoke activism resulted in *Clean Air Acts* across multiple urbanised states, starting in Britain and later adopted in America and Europe.

Compared to other geographies, BC came late to air pollution activism. Urban centres on the coast, particularly Victoria and Vancouver, had long benefited from Pacific winds that blew pollution away from populated areas. Citizens and municipal governments were nevertheless influenced by the smoke

25. Thomas Dunlap and Frank Uekotter, *The Age of Smoke: Environmental Policy in Germany and the United States, 1880–1970* (Pittsburgh: University of Pittsburgh Press, 2009), pp. 1–2.

26. Peter Thorsheim, *Inventing Pollution: Coal, Smoke, and Culture in Britain Since 1800* (Athens: Ohio University Press, 2006), pp. 6–7; Stephen Mosley, *The Chimney of the World: A History of Smoke Pollution in Victorian and Edwardian Manchester* (Taylor and Francis, 2013), p. 27; Angela Gugliotta, 'Class, gender, and coal smoke: Gender ideology and environmental injustice in Pittsburgh, 1868–1914', *Environmental History* 5 (2) (2000): 165–93; Sarah Lynn Cunningham, 'From smoke-filled skies to smoke-filled rooms: Louisville's political battles over the "smoke evil"', *Ohio Valley History* (Spring 2008): 67.

abatement efforts of international counterparts, adopting the Ringelmann chart as part of 1920s restrictions on burning and, as air pollution rhetoric matured, adopting the arguments of neighbours in the US and Europe.²⁷ Local businessmen and professionals (largely representing service and professional industries rather than manufacturing) formed the Air Pollution Control Society in 1952 to advocate for pollution control largely based (at first) on its economic impacts related to cleaning buildings, delaying flights and discouraging tourism.²⁸ By the 1960s and 1970s, rising concern about air pollution brought widespread attention to smoke of all kinds in BC.

Urban environmental historians have classically understood cities as ecosystems within ecosystems, so that efforts to reduce pollution within one sphere tended to transfer harm rather than eliminate it.²⁹ Forest smoke presents questions about control over the air, jurisdiction, and relationships between urban and rural spaces. For example, Elizabeth Jones' work on German moor burning talks about the tensions between rural burning traditions and urban sensibilities as smoke unpredictably drifted across the country.³⁰ Lee Thiessen's history of urban air pollution in southern BC grapples with peoples' periodic frustrations with slash smoke and its ultimate exclusion from smoke abatement regulations in metro Vancouver.³¹ The Northwest Air Pollution Authority instituted agricultural burning bans in Washington in response to urban complaints in the 1960s and 1970s, and the same organisation complained to the BC Forest Service that its slash smoke was drifting south into the Nooksack Valley in 1972 (The BC Forest Service for its part denied burning in the border area).³² Smoke was not alone in the way that it crossed jurisdictional boundaries. Other mediums, especially water have enjoyed similarly contentious pasts. In BC, damming the Skagit River became a source of tension across the Canada–US border, and the question of salmon migration on the Fraser a controversy between the river's urban mouth and its headwaters deep in the provincial interior.³³

27. Lee Thiessen, 'Protesting smoke: A social and political history of Vancouver air pollution in the 1950s and 1960s', *Urban History Review* 46 (1) (2017): 57–70.

28. Thiessen, 'Protesting smoke', 60–61.

29. Joel Tarr, *The Search for the Ultimate Sink: Urban Pollution in Historical Perspective* (University of Akron Press, 1996).

30. Elizabeth Jones, 'No smoke without fire: Moor burning, the environment, and social reform in the German Empire, 1866–1914', *Agricultural History* 88 (2) (2004): 20–36.

31. Thiessen, 'Protesting smoke', 57–70.

32. 'Fog Causing Difficulty', *The Sun*, 19 Oct. 1972, 2.

33. Phil Van Huizen, 'Flooding the Border: Development, Politics, and Environmental Controversy in the Canadian-U.S. Skagit Valley', Ph.D. Diss., UBC, 2013; Matthew Evenden, *Fish Versus Power: An Environmental History of the Fraser River* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2007).

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Power relations normally determine the flow of harm within and between human communities.³⁴ In cities, the pollution experienced by poor, racialised and working-class neighbourhoods stemmed from intentional choices made about the position of factories and effluent pipes under weak regulations by people with an interest in maximising profits. In theory, wildfires strike randomly and without the burdens of cultural prejudice to guide them, and so should be equal-opportunity polluters. Yet scholars working from intersectional and environmental justice standpoints have shown that today's forest fires impact people unequally.³⁵ With large indigenous and working-class populations, resource communities in BC's interior were demographically and culturally different from their counterparts on the coast. Northern communities engaged with air pollution issues differently from their urban counterparts. Part of this difference included a longer and more intimate relationship with smoke. For example, while wood heat had largely been done away with in urban centres the world over, the people who occupied most of BC's interior communities continued to live in homes heated with wood and lit by oil.³⁶ Energy historian Josh MacFadyen argues that Canadians were 'hewers of wood' who reached 'peak wood' in the middle of twentieth century, a time otherwise renowned for its shift to coal and fossil fuels among the world's nation states.³⁷ In BC's north, the ubiquitous forestry sector generated smoke

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34. Rob Nixon, *Slow Violence and the Environmentalism of the Poor* (Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 2011); Gugliotta, 'Class, gender, and coal smoke'; Melanie Dupuis, *Smoke and Mirrors: The Politics and Culture of Air Pollution* (New York: NYU Press, 2004).
35. Christine Eriksen et. al., 'The gendered dimensions of bushfire in changing rural landscapes in Australia', *Journal of Rural Studies* **26** (2010): 332–42; Heidi Walker et. al., 'Social dimensions of climate hazards in rural communities of the Global North: An intersectionality framework', *Journal of Rural Studies* **72** (2019): 1–10; Alex Zahara, 'Breathing fire into landscapes that burn: Wildfire management in a time of alterlife', *Engaging Science, Technology, and Society* **8** (2020): 555–85. Ian Davies et. al., 'The unequal vulnerability of communities of color to wildfire', *PloS One* **13** (11) (2018): E0205825; Prateek Shrestha et. al., 'Impact of outdoor air pollution on indoor air quality in low-income homes during wildfire seasons', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* **16** (19) (2019): 3535.
36. For example, Buster Brown recalls living at Willow River in the 1920s in a home heated with wood, and switching to kerosene over time because it smoked less than coal and oil. Buster Brown, interviewed by Rhys Pugh and Laura Ryser, 8 June 2000, Upper Fraser Historical Geography Project, File 2017.6.1.10, NBCA. When Chrissie Ward immigrated to northern BC from England in 1927 to marry a logger, she recalled struggling with the wood stove. 'I was not used to putting wood in a stove', she explained. Chrissie Ward, interviewed by Dan Watt, Prince George, 26 June 2000, Upper Fraser Historical Geography Project, File 2017.6.1.72, NBCA.
37. Joshua MacFadyen, 'Hewers of wood: A history of wood energy in Canada', in Ruth Sandwell (ed), *Powering up Canada: A History of Power, Fuel, and Energy from 1600* (Montreal: McGill-Queen's University Press, 2016), pp. 129–61.

and steam from logging operations, mills, beehives and slash.³⁸ In places like Trail or Kitimat, forest smoke would mix with smoke from smelters.³⁹ While urban populations, particularly racialised and working class neighbourhoods, struggled with factory smoke, rural and resource communities experienced disproportionate smoke loads from this combination of industrial, forestry and natural ignitions. Moreover, both the intentionally produced smoke generated by the forestry industry and the unintentional smoke from unchecked wildfires burning near remote indigenous communities can be seen as part of wider colonial land relations in BC.⁴⁰

Before World War II, the prevalence of smoke in peoples' day-to-day lives can be read in the district foresters' account of the view from the Forest Service's first lookout at Mount Baker: 'During the dangerous season it was noticed that the air is normally sufficiently clear to [spot forest fire smoke]', but other times of year, there was so much smoke in the air that wild columns became easy to miss.⁴¹ Slash burning clouded the air in the spring and fall when farmers, road builders and logging companies were issued burning permits by the Forest Service. During bad fire years, resource communities lived under blankets of combined industrial and wildfire smoke for weeks at a time. As lumbermen and farmers struggled to contain the Mud River fire in 1922 from destroying several farms and properties in the area, the BC Forest Service was busy burning logging slash. The *Prince George Citizen* reported that 'while the situation in the merchantable timber areas is reported to be better, by the forest department, the burning of old slashed over country and of promising young timber that would be of value for pulp purposes, is filling the whole country with an oppressive pall of smoke'.⁴²

After World War II, complaints about forest smoke intensified in both northern resource communities and urban metropolises in BC, but the stakes for each were different. By the 1960s, dissatisfaction about air pollution from mills made regular appearances in community newspapers and some rural municipalities contemplated bylaws to curb the worst offenders.⁴³ While Victoria residents complained that 'if the atmosphere has not cleared by this after-

38. Special thanks to Claudette Gauger at the University of Northern British Columbia, who generously shared parts of her forthcoming Masters research on planer and pulp mill pollution in Prince George.

39. Arn Keeling, 'The Effluent Society: Water Pollution and Environmental Politics in British Columbia, 1889–1980', Ph.D. diss., University of British Columbia, 2004, pp. 178–79; Keith Murray, 'The trail smelter: International air pollution in the Colombia Valley', *BC Studies* 15 (Autumn 1972): 68–85; John Wirth, *Smelter Smoke in North America: The Politics of Transborder Pollution* (Lawrence: University Press of Kansas, 2000).

40. This is the first argument of Max Liboiron's *Pollution is Colonialism* (Durham: Duke University Press, 2021), p. 6.

41. Province of BC, *Report of the Forest Branch, Department of Lands, 1914* (Victoria: King's Printer, 1915), p. 100.

42. 'Fires in All Directions Create Heavy Smoke Pall', *Prince George Citizen*, 13 June 1922.

43. 'Council Getting Tough on Pollution Problem', *The Citizen*, 21 July 1966, 1.

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noon, the 45-minute aerobatic display of the RCAF's Golden Centenaries will probably be cancelled',⁴⁴ the mill town of Port Alberni prepared to evacuate and Tofino and Ucluelet got completely cut off as the fire crossed the only road into their communities.⁴⁵ Pollution often hindered suppression efforts, leading to even worse conditions. 'One of the greatest bugbears to firefighters and citizens in the Kamloops and Prince George areas is the dense black smoke given off by the scores of forest fires', *The Province* explained in 1961 – 'the ceiling at Prince George airport where water bombers have to land and take off is only 800 feet. Visibility from forest outlook posts is down to half a mile in smoke spots.' A group of high school students from Toronto lamented that the murk from the interior ruined their sightseeing tour. Meanwhile, the fires threatened Ingenika River and surrounded Prince Rupert, Smithers, Chapman Lake, Houston, Telegraph Creek, Gunnanoot Lake and a sawmill community on Potlatch Creek. 'We badly need more aircraft, but we don't know where to get them', was the hopeless answer of Prince Rupert's district protection officer S.T. Strimbald when asked about the dozens of out-of-control fires in the provincial interior.⁴⁶ In places close to out-of-control fires, smoke could mean the loss of lives, property and work while smoke carried into urban spaces meant inconvenience and annoyance. Such instances illustrate how northern and resource communities bore the physical, economic and psychological burdens of wildfire and smoke differently from their urban counterparts.

Poor air quality persisted in rural municipalities long after air pollution regulations improved conditions in the cities of the provincial south. In the 1980s, the BC Forest Service celebrated improvements to the forestry town of Prince George's air quality by pointing out that, until the 1960s, the planer mills 'belched smoke and a lot of half-burned sawdust into the air'. By the 1980s,

Residents no longer sweep singed sawdust off their cars when they get up in the morning. Sawdust fallout has been replaced by the sulphurous odour emanating from the pulp mills. But the prevailing wind usually blows the smell away from the city. Residents say they are only bothered by it when an inversion happens.⁴⁷

44. 'Smoke Blots Sky', *The Daily Colonist*, 19 Aug. 1967, section 2, 17.

45. 'I remember the smoke mushroomed into the sky', recalled one local on the 50th anniversary of the fire. Another said, 'it looked like an atom bomb'. It took decades for the land to recover. Susie Quinn, '50 Years Later, Alberni Loffer Recalls Taylor River Fire', *Alberni Valley News*, 16 Aug. 2017: <https://www.alberni-valley-news.com/news/50-years-later-alberni-log-ger-recalls-taylor-river-fire/> (accessed 3 June 2021).

46. 'Blaze Threatening Indian Community in Northern BC', 'Forest Fire Smoke Hides City Scenery', *The Province* 14 Aug. 1961, 3.

47. 'Of the nine major lumber-producing regions in North America, Prince George ranks second', *ForesTalk* (Fall 1978): 20.

Such efforts suggest that peoples' expectations and experiences of air pollution were substantively different in the communities of BC's rural and resource-industry dependent interior from those in the more economically diverse and abatement-sensitive coastal cities.

Just as urban pollution generated a distinct environmentalism among working class people, smoke abatement activism took on a different character in the rural north from that in Vancouver and Victoria, especially as city-dwellers became less dependent on the natural resource industries that drove the rest of the province.⁴⁸ Smoke in resource communities, whether wild or industrial, was part of the price one paid for wealth – hence the aphorism often used to dismiss concerns about polluted air: 'It's the smell of money.'⁴⁹ 'Even those most disturbed by unpleasant smells would not suggest northern industry stop because of an odour they don't like nor should they suggest expensive means to reduce smells which might only have small effect', read one Prince George editorial on the matter of noxious mill smoke. 'On the other hand, few would deny the city has a problem ... [and] should be seeking means to cut down contributions to a dirty sky.'⁵⁰ Where livelihoods depended on a single industry and work was seasonal or temporary, people tended to think about environmental hazards, including all kinds of smoke generated in the woods, as part of a risk-reward balance.⁵¹

48. As Jeremy Wilson puts it, 'residents of forest-dependent communities were left to rail against the "cappuccino-sucking, concrete condo dwelling, granola-eating" city slicker environmentalists threatening their livelihoods', Wilson, *Talk and Log*, p. xiv.

49. A quote attributed to premier W.A.C. Bennet during a tour of northern British Columbia. Malcolm Gray, 'The Lovely Smell that's Gone Away', *Macleans*, 17 Aug. 1981: <https://archive.macleans.ca/article/1981/8/17/the-lovely-smell-thats-gone-away> (accessed 11 June 2021)). The smell of money is a common trope in industry towns the world over. See Kerri Arseneault, *Mill Town: Reckoning with What Remains* (New York: St Martins, 2020); Jill Stainsby, 'It's the smell of money: Women shoreworkers of British Columbia', *BC Studies* 103 (Fall 1994): 59–81; Laurie Mercier, "Gender, labour and place: Reconstructing women's spaces in industrial communities of Western Canada and the United States", *Labour History* 53 (3): 389–407.

50. 'A Breath of Fresh Air', *The Citizen*, 17 April 1964, 9.

51. Workers in primary industries historically accepted more risk, as has been explored by Karen Buckley, *Danger, Death, and Disaster in the Crownsnest Pass Mines, 1902–1928* (Calgary: University of Calgary Press, 2004); Jacqueline Kirkham, 'Forsaking Paul Bunyan: A Gendered Analysis of Forestry Company Safety Policy on Vancouver Island in the Mid-Twentieth Century', Ph.D. diss., McMaster University, 2017; James Lawson, 'Explaining workplace injuries among BC loggers: Cultures of risk and desperation' *BC Studies* 164 (Winter 2009/2010): 51–74. Christopher Sellers, *Hazards of the Job: From Industrial Disease to Environmental Health Science* (Chapel Hill: University of North Carolina Press, 1997).

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BURNING FOR CLEAN AIR IN BC'S SUPPRESSION ERA

It is no coincidence that the rise of interest in clean air coincided with the cresting of wildfire suppression in BC. As an agency, the Forest Service in BC was sympathetic to environmentalism, particularly the conservationist principles that had originated in scientific forestry. At a time when environmental messaging enjoyed widespread popularity in the province, its anti-fire message benefited from association with anti-pollution principles and the Forest Service enthusiastically framed its efforts in these terms. Starting in the 1950s it launched an aggressive radio, television and print campaign that encouraged vigilance in the woods among citizens. In BC, citizens were entreated to 'report all suspicious smoke'. That smoke was antithetical to healthy environments made logical sense in the context of industrial smoke abatement in the province's urban centres.

Yet wildfire management and the continuation of the forestry industry in BC required a significant amount of smoke production, and the Forest Service had not considered that most British Columbians could not usefully differentiate between 'suspicious' and 'unsuspicious' smoke. The Forest Service was

Figure 1. 'Gallows Sign, Manning Park', 1950, Forest Service Photographs, Image NA-10374, courtesy of the Royal BC Museum.

not interested in curbing its own use of fire, but the use of fire by all *other* forest users. It had a specific type of forest user in mind, to whom it apportioned blame for waste and destruction in the woods while ignoring the smoke and escaped fires that billowed from their own burns: The ‘careless smoker’ was an inexperienced recreationist, using the woods for leisure without thought for the economic devastation a fire could cause. In 1945, Chief Justice Sloan’s Commission on the Forest Resources of BC included a lengthy discussion of how increased recreational use was leading to a greater fire menace in the woods.⁵² The Forest Service pursued ‘rigorous prosecutions for infractions’, starting in 1950.⁵³ In some cases, judgemental indictments of the ‘careless smoker’ went so far as to imply that infractions would be punished by hanging, although the Forest Service of course had no such power (see Figure 1).

In the 1960s, a television ad showed a middle-aged man in a mustang throwing a cigarette out the window. ‘Everyone is aware of the pall of smoke that obscures the sun’, the voiceover explains. ‘Fifty cents of every dollar in BC comes from the forest. We all have a responsibility to look after it.’⁵⁴ The intended message was that British Columbians should take personal interest in protecting the forestry industry by reporting unauthorised ignitions to the qualified professionals in the Forest Service.

Anti-smoke messaging worked. Its success can be measured in rising smoke anxiety among BC’s public and the tightening of control by its Forest Service. In Prince George, rumours of a large wildfire near town spread until the Forest Service confirmed that the local smoke pall had drifted in from fires further north.⁵⁵ In Port Alberni in 1967, ‘the odour of burning wood’ sent ‘horrified householders’ rushing out, ‘unaware that it was smoke carried on the wind, and not coming from burning timber nearby’.⁵⁶ In 1974, the BC Forest Service lamented the fact that wildfires continued to plague the province ‘in excess of 2000 each year’. Yet they congratulated themselves on their initial attack programme which ‘has reduced the extent of most of the wildfires so that little such smoke persists to obscure summer scenery’.⁵⁷ The rise in ignitions was framed as a failure of the public, and the success of suppression evidence that the Forest Service was capable of keeping up with both the growing negligence of recreationists and the vagrancies of nature. Smoke had become a sophisticated tool for suppression, so that the barest whiff on the breeze could

52. Province of BC, *Report of the Commissioner, The Honourable Gordon Sloan, Chief Justice of British Columbia, relating to The Forest Resources of British Columbia, 1945* (Victoria: King’s Printer, 1945), p. 140.

53. Province of BC, *Report of the Forest Service, 1950* (Victoria: Kings Printer, 1951), p. 60.

54. ‘Up in Smoke’, British Columbia Forest Service Public Information and Education Division, directed by Barbara Davis, 1968, F1987:01/015, RBCA.

55. ‘Smoke Pall’, *Prince George Citizen*, 25 May 1953, 1.

56. ‘Smoke Blots Sky’, *The Daily Colonist*, 19 Aug. 1967, section 2, 17

57. Province of BC, *Report of the Forest Service, Year Ended December 31, 1974* (Victoria: King’s Printer, 1975), p. 37.

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be instantly responded to while the Forest Service could reasonably claim near perfect control of all ignitions.

This narrative of success against destructive wildfire and its polluting smokes did not account for the Forest Service's own burning activities, which often overlapped with wild ignitions and continued to produce significant nuisance smoke in BC communities. Then as now, landscape management required a certain amount of smoke production to dispose of wastes and clear excess fuels. Public audiences lectured for decades on the danger of forest fire, trained to report visible smoke, and amid new debates about regulating air pollution, were understandably alarmed when they saw plumes of slash smoke rising from the forests or drifting into the cities. Yet the Forest Service dismissed community concerns about the spread of their own slash fires near the recently devastated Brentwood Bay as 'unwarranted'. They also burned a considerable area on the Malahat highway north of Victoria, a busy transportation route, causing significant alarm for residents and travellers.⁵⁸

Figure 2. Forest Service Newsletter 65 (Oct. 1947) (08581): 1

'British Columbians should be thankful for slash burning', the Forest Service told *The Province* in 1968. Resources Minister Ray Williston told the *Sun* that

if we don't burn it now under controlled conditions, the slash will present an extreme fire hazard in the forests next summer and if one large fire gets away on us we could have a lot more smoke in the air than now. A really bad fire could put a small cloud over most of the continent.

58. 'Alarm Caused by Big Slash Fires in Nearby Areas', *Victoria Daily Times*, 20 Sept. 1947, 1.

He cited the 1950 Chinchaga fire as an example (neglecting to mention that the Forest Service had explicitly chosen to let Chinchaga burn). A gap opened between the smoke-free world the Forest Service described and the reality of ongoing haze experienced by British Columbians.

In 1973, the Eden Fire dropped like a match into the tinder of ongoing tensions over suppression, smoke and air pollution in BC. That year, a slash burn started by a forestry company escaped into the surrounding trees. The BC Forest Service responded, but without enthusiasm. Because fire generally moves upwards on ridges, there was no perceived danger to nearby values. However, strong winds drove the fire unexpectedly down into the populated Gleneden valley, where it caused more than a million dollars worth of damage to sixteen homes, a collection of farms and timber spread over 16,000 acres.

At another time or place in BC history, the Eden fire might have been just another disaster. But Gleneden was a retirement community, containing a collection of former Vancouver residents who had left the city for the provincial interior in search of a quiet life close to nature. As the investigative report that followed the Eden Fire concluded, ‘many people came to live here, seeking a quiet “non-fast” way of life. These people ... don’t want industry and what comes with it.’⁵⁹ The angry letters they wrote to the Ministry in the fire’s aftermath indicates that ‘what comes with it’ included smoke pollution. ‘I am writing this note in a state of frustration and anger as I watch a smoke-filled sky – a red sun – still high in the cloudless afternoon sky – and ponder your department’s incompetence’, began one letter to the Minister in the summer of that year (original emphasis). ‘Not only does this type of slash removal create environmental havoc – pollute the air – but is extremely dangerous.’⁶⁰ Chris Raith, a small-scale logger, noted that ‘the Indians burned in the spring when the snow melted and the ground was damp’, and blamed the influence of big forestry companies for the fact that the Forest Service was not wise enough to do the same.⁶¹ Vince Hale of Vancouver suggested that logging slash be stacked and cut up for firewood: ‘The smoke produced would be mostly washed away by the rains (besides wood smoke doesn’t smell as bad).’⁶² Pat Gee, recently moved to Salmon Arm from the city, wrote that she had

felt ever since I moved here, that slash burning generally must be stopped. Each fall the atmosphere around the area has been polluted with a pall of smoke

59. G.B. Turner, ‘B. Conclusions of citizens interviewed’, *The Eden Fire: Salmon Arm; British Columbia, September 1973 Book One*, Report Prepared for the Honourable Robert Williams, Minister, Department of Lands, Forests and Water Resources, Government of the Province of British Columbia, Jan. 1974.

60. Bernard Smith to The Minister, Department of Lands and Forests, 18 Sept. 1973, Series GR-1227 – All – Correspondence Controversial Topics, file 5, RBCA.

61. Chris Raith to the Honourable Bob Williams, 17 Sept. 1973, Series GR-1227 – All – Correspondence Controversial Topics, file 5, RBCA.

62. Vince Hale to Premier Barrett, 18 Sept. 1973, Series GR-1227 – All – Correspondence Controversial Topics, file 5, RBCA.

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that many times one can't even see the hills across the lake and each year the *Salmon Arm Observer* has a number of letters from tourists deploring this archaic procedure.⁶³

The Forest Service insisted it was not responsible for the smoke (or the damaging fire) because Glen Eden had been a wildfire. 'Even the most experienced fire manager would not have foreseen the peculiar combination of wind, topography, time of day, and fuel distribution' that drove the fire into the Gleneden valley, it claimed. It pointed to the large amounts of slash still on the landscape and argued that, not only should the Forest Service keep burning, but should do so with more and greater resources. Okanagan residents felt differently: 'nature did not instigate the Eden Fire; man did'.⁶⁴ They challenged the Forest Service's unmitigated licence to pollute the air in the name of fuel management.

Indeed, while the Forest Service adopted the position that 'slash usually burns briskly and without much smoke', human experience differed.⁶⁵ With only a few days or weeks with the right humidity and wind conditions to facilitate controlled burns, slash smoke generally came on cool clear days when urban people were spending time outside and when venting smoke was most visible and least desirable. Moreover, since slash was usually burned in fall, it functioned to extend the smoke season at times when people might have still been carrying recent trauma from the wildfires that had burned the land during the dry season.⁶⁶ Studies of urban smoke suggest that fall was the time of year when cities were most likely to suffer from industrial smog during temperature inversions, in which case slash smoke aggravated existing urban pollution.⁶⁷

The integration of slash smoke into the question of air pollution represented a shift in the focus of abatement activism. Although forest smoke (both controlled and uncontrolled) had always contributed to pollution loads, smoke abatement efforts had historically opted for easier targets. City officials distinguished between industrial smoke they could target with regulation as opposed to wood smoke generated in the forests: 'Wood burning doesn't do anybody any harm. Our pioneers and forefathers put up with plenty of wood smoke. It's industrial fumes which are injurious to health that I'm worried about', commented Alderman Halford Wilson in 1968, during the height of abatement

63. Pat Gee to the Minister of Lands, Forests and Water Resources, 21 Sept. 1973, Series GR-1227 – All – Correspondence Controversial Topics, file 5, RBCA.

64. D.B. Turner, 'A. Main conclusions', *The Eden Fire: Salmon Arm; British Columbia, September 1973 Book One*, Report Prepared for the Honourable Robert Williams, Minister, Department of Lands, Forests and Water Resources, Government of the Province of British Columbia, Jan. 1974.

65. 'A Large Column of Smoke' *Victoria Daily Times*, 30 April 1938, 13; 'Over All Lines', *Victoria Daily Times*, 4 Oct. 1941, 12; 'Smoke Pall Due to Slash Fires', *The Vancouver Daily Province*, 17 Sept. 1947, 2.

66. Theissen, 'Protesting smoke', 59.

67. Mosley, *The Chimney of the World*, p. 27.

rhetoric in Vancouver.⁶⁸ The urban areas of BC had a pollution problem because of automobiles and industry, the Forest Service asserted in the mid-1970s. Wildfire and slash smoke ‘may not increase the hazard but it certainly makes the situation far more noticeable’.⁶⁹ Thus when medical health officers were given powers to limit polluting industries, slash burning remained excluded.⁷⁰

Although rising environmentalism in BC at first proved a useful vehicle for spreading the message of fire suppression, after the Eden fire it became a curse. The Forest Service increasingly found itself defending its own smoke production against a sceptical public who used its own rhetoric against it. A different, more nuanced fire prevention message was needed if the public was to be brought back inside – one that was not connected to hated smoke. Eden was not the only front on which the Forest Service battled critique: In the 1970s, British Columbians were also questioning the power of the forestry industry generally to determine how BC’s forests were valued, and particularly questioned the liquidation of old growth stands.⁷¹ Starting in 1973, in the immediate aftermath of Gleneden, *ForesTalk* magazine was meant to accomplish these goals. ‘In these times of so much freedom there are many organizations and individuals who are openly and often emotionally critical of government’, reads the opening editorial of the magazine’s first edition. ‘Too often [criticism] is made without the full facts or understanding’, so *ForesTalk* would be aimed at ‘the average reader’ and ‘distributed free of charge to all schools in B.C.’ Its first issue celebrated the fact that the agency burned 430 acres of slash within fifteen miles of downtown Vancouver in 1972 –without anyone noticing – forwarding a message of scientific control over forest smoke.⁷²

The effort to popularise a more nuanced wildfire prevention message in BC would continue into the 1980s. In an article titled ‘A New Look at Fire’, the Forest Service’s public newsletter told readers that ‘it’s been difficult teaching an old bear new tricks, but now that Smokey is a fire ecologist, he’ll be the first to tell you that not all forest fires are bad’.⁷³ Don Owen, former director of the Ministry of Forest’s Protection Branch reassured readers that ‘we will only allow fire where we can control it’. This meant letting wildfires burn where they would benefit land management objectives as well as ‘setting a fire to achieve certain effects – prescribed burning’.⁷⁴ Although Owen admitted that slash burning was one of the main reasons the Forest Service lit fires, he chose to emphasise its potential to encourage forest regrowth while opening

68. ‘There’s Ire With Smoke from Slash’, *The Sunday Sun*, 7 Sept. 1968, 29.

69. Province of BC, *Report of the Forest Service Year Ended December 31st, 1974* (Victoria: King’s Printer, 1975), p. 37.

70. ‘Pollution’, *The Province*, 7 Sept. 1968, 2.

71. Wilson, *Talk and Log*, xvii.

72. ‘New rules and a new technique for slash burning’ *ForesTalk* 1 (1) (1973): 12.

73. ‘A New Look at Fire’, *ForesTalk* 5 (2) (1981): 23.

74. *Ibid.*, 24

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Figure 3. 'Unfavourable and Favourable Burning Conditions', *ForesTalk* 1 (1) (1973): 13.

range and wildlife habitat. In the same article, almost a decade after Gleneden, Brad Hawkes of the Canadian Forestry service defended the use of fire in the valley that fateful day. The problem was not the tool, but the way it was used, he claimed: burning must remain in the hands of the Service's trained professionals. By now the Forest Service openly rued the power of its smoke-centred messaging. Responding publicly to new American research on the health hazards of slash smoke, spokesman Peter Bell said, 'the Smokey-the-Bear advertising theme that no forest fire is a good fire has been an effective but extremely harmful advertising campaign ... because slash burning fires are necessary'.⁷⁵ Yet, without the shorthand of anti-smoke rhetoric, this more complex message of scientific management remained unconvincing to BC's public.

75. 'New Health Hazard in B.C. Forest Slash Burning', *The Province*, 11 Oct. 1978, 4.

THE LEGACY OF ABATEMENT IN A WORLD ON FIRE

In 1985, smoke like Chinchaga once again circulated the northern hemisphere as wildfires raged in western Canada. ‘That sooty pall above the smokestacks of Birmingham and Liverpool may actually be smoke from a B.C. forest fire’, read *The Province* that year. This time around, there was no mystery about its origin – Dr. Y.S. Chung, a research scientist with Environment Canada traced the plume with satellite imagery. But if the origins of smoke had become easier to identify, its meanings had only become more complex. Chung was interested in the smoke as part of his research on the possible impacts of nuclear winter. To others, his findings described ‘a huge area of pollution heading for Europe across the Atlantic’ and suggested ‘a need for international control of acid rain and other air pollution problems’.⁷⁶ Meanwhile, the town of Canal Flats in BC’s interior watched the flames advance on town. ‘Most of us are used to fighting fires’, said local resident Wayne Agnew, but this year was different. ‘We can’t see a damn thing for the smoke. Cinders are falling all around.’⁷⁷ ‘The smoke is giving us breathing problems’, agreed Margaret Nissen, who had been forced to evacuate.⁷⁸ Then, in September, the Forest Service let two slash fires get out of control in Sechelt and Duncan when ‘ideal conditions’ turned into ‘a sudden weather change that brought drier air and gusting winds’.⁷⁹ In Kelowna, the city council voted unanimously to ask the forestry ministry to stop issuing permits to forest companies for burning slash. Smoke delayed flights and, according to fruit growers, delayed the ripening of apple and grape crops.⁸⁰

In the face of critique stemming from these and other incidences, the Ministry held its ground. ‘Burning is necessary for forest companies to remove slash timber, which poses a fire hazard’, a representative of the Forest Service explained, ‘and to prepare ground for replanting operations’.⁸¹ In the intervening decades, it had proved unable to control either smoke or its critics as it attempted to draw boundaries between ‘good’ and ‘bad’ smoke in the ash-laden air. Its inability to control the meaning of smoke for those who witnessed it shows the power of urban air pollution rhetoric to exert influence far beyond municipal boundaries.

In BC we can see how smoke moved between urban spaces and forests with unequal impacts for individuals and communities. As a case study, BC’s smoke history shows how forest smoke became entangled with rising late-twentieth century environmental sentiment, particularly around urban air

76. ‘B.C. Fires Polluting Britain?’ *The Province*, 6 Aug. 1985, 13.

77. ‘Forest Inferno Threatens Town’, *The Province*, 7 July 1985, 3.

78. ‘Smoke Forces Families Out’, *The Province*, 8 July 1985, A2.

79. ‘Two B.C. Slash Fires Flare Out of Control’, *The Sun*, 28 Sept. 1985, A2.

80. ‘Kelowna Seeks Ban on Burning’, *The Sun*, 2 Oct. 1985, A13.

81. *Ibid.*

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pollution. As the product of a confusing collection of human and non-human factors outside of the cities, forest smoke provided a tricky problem for abatement efforts. Although forest smoke constituted a nuisance at best and a health threat at worst, a forest could not be fined for failing to keep emissions within acceptable limits and land managers could not be held accountable for the vagaries of nature. Yet slash burning and events like the Eden Fire suggested to a smoke-phobic public that burning was done mostly in the interest of industrial forestry rather than communities, and that the Forest Service could reasonably assume some responsibility for the resulting pollution.

In the late twentieth century, the Forest Service's choice to connect suppression messaging to environmental principles threatened to undermine its freedom to burn in BC. As they focussed educational campaigns on reforming the 'careless smoker', the Forest Service had failed to account for the growing disconnect between what they practised (which included setting lots of fires and generating lots of smoke) and what they preached (which encouraged people to report all smoke to aid suppression). As the province's most important land manager, the Forest Service benefited from smoke's ephemerality, but that same characteristic also made it vulnerable to blame. In a context intolerant of air pollution, the Forest Service was forced to work hard to carve out a space for its own burning while distancing itself from the kinds of uncontrolled fires that continued to burden communities with unwanted carbon. It proved unable to influence the way that environmental rhetoric, once invoked, would work against it in subsequent efforts to assert scientific control over BC's forests.

The Wildfire Service in BC continues to walk a fine line governed by our expectations for clean environments and the needs of a forestry industry which underpins the provincial economy. Forest smoke occupies an awkward space in the public imagination. The problem was (and remains) a cultural one, rooted in expectations of smoke-free environments built over time and the parallel need to periodically burn boreal ecologies to prevent catastrophic wildfire. Given the enormous distances forest smoke can travel, understanding its nature it has never been more critical. Forest smoke has historically been understood as the product of natural disaster rather than the responsibility of forest management agencies who nominally control them. As escalating anthropogenic climate change challenges the boundaries between nature and culture, such explanations may prove increasingly unsatisfying to people living with the smoky legacy of suppression. Wildfire services in BC and elsewhere are moving toward models of community-led land management and prescribed fire – which will mean more smoke, not less. For these initiatives to succeed, the Forest Service will need to relinquish its narrative of control and British Columbians will need to become more tolerant of forest smoke.

